

Funded by
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MYRTUS

Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems

Deliverable:

D13.1- Project quality handbook

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Responsible: Maria Katuscia Zedda (Abinsula)

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1 Executive Summary

D13.1 – Project quality handbook – M3 – Task Involved: T13.1

This deliverable provides the templates on the project management process, review process, quality checks, meetings organisation, etc.

2 Management Structure

2.1 General Assembly

The **General Assembly** is the decision-making body of the consortium. It consists of one representative of each Party. The GA supervises the project, and it's chaired by the project coordinator.

*The description of the General Assembly, its Members, and Operational Procedures that rule its duties are describes in the **Consortium Agreement – Section 6 – Governance structure.***

2.2 Project Coordinator

The **Project Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The **Scientific Coordinator** is an identified person supporting the Project Coordinator in the scientific project management.

The Project Coordinator is Dr. Maria Katuscia Zedda (katuscia.zedda@abinsula.com).

The Scientific Coordinator is Prof. Francesca Palumbo (francesca.palumbo@unica.it).

*The project Coordinator and its duties are described in the **Consortium Agreement – Section 6.4 – Coordinator.***

2.3 Workpackage Leaders

The **Workpackage (WP) Leaders** are responsible for the organization and control of each workpackage. The task leaders are the identified people supporting the Workpackage leaders in the duties. Some of the WP leaders' responsibilities are:

- Coordinate the work carried out on the work package.
- Set up the procedures needed to monitor and identify possible problems.

- Plan and chair work package telcos where the work package members can align and discuss technical progress.
- Report progress and plan activities to the project board.

It is responsibility of the WP leader to monitor the WP and to advise the Project Coordinator of potential delay that could have a negative impact on a deliverable and in general on the achievements of the project.

The list of the WP and Task leaders can be consulted in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Organisation->Consortium->Reference contacts.xlsx*.

For an overview on how to navigate the Shared Drive Folder, consult *Section 4.2 – Project repository of this document*.

2.4 Deliverable Leaders

The **Deliverable Leaders** are responsible for organizing, collecting contributions, editing and delivering their deliverables in time, following the process defined in *Section 3.5 – Deliverable* of this document.

The list of institutions leading each deliverable is reported in the **Grant Agreement** (Table *LIST OF DELIVERABLES*).

The responsible's names are reported in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Official Documents -> Final deliverables -> Deliverable Leaders and Reviewers.xlsx*.

For an overview on how to navigate the Shared Drive Folder, consult *Section 4.2 – Project repository of this document*.

3 Project Monitoring and information flow

The project is monitored through:

- Periodic meetings, at different levels of granularity.
- Project reviews.
- Deliverables.

3.1 Mailing list

Day-to-day communication will be based on emails. The following mailing lists have been set up to facilitate communication among partners and diffusion of general internal project information:

- MYRTUS general
- MYRTUS WP1-WP2
- MYRTUS WP3-WP4
- MYRTUS WP5-WP6
- MYRTUS WP7-WP8
- MYRTUS WP9-WP10

Furthermore, a MYRTUS google account has been created to manage MYRTUS social media, will be also used for collecting **inputs for communication and dissemination**.

To help all partners to efficiently deal with MYRTUS related communications and to quickly recognize the significance of an e-mail, the e-mails should include the **[MYRTUS]** label.

To add/remove a person from the list, edit the mailing list file in the Shared Folder, and inform Tiziana Fanni or Katuscia Zedda of the change made.

The MYRTUS Mailing list file is in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Organization->Consortium->MYRTUS mailing list.*

3.2 Meetings

Regular e-mail contact, telephone or WP online meetings should be held to support the cooperation among partners working in the same work package. Each WP Leader should organize regular conference calls with Task leaders and partners involved in the work package, to monitor performance and progress with respect to the project timetables defined in the *Grant Agreement, Section 3.1 – Work plan and resources*. The frequency of the calls may change depending on the needs.

The Project Coordinator should organize **monthly conf-calls** to support the cooperation among partners working in different work packages.

A **plenary meeting** will be held twice a year, one virtual meeting and one Face-2-Face meeting (F2F).

The goal of these meetings is both to report and align:

- on the administrative and managerial duties and deadlines.
- on the technical work at project level.

When the meeting is F2F, a short virtual meeting will be organised a week in advance, to align on the administrative issue and exploit the F2F meeting only for technical activities.

The following list of meeting is currently envisioned:

Period	Meeting	Host	Mode
6-8 February 2024	Kick-Off Meeting	Abinsula	F2F
July 2024	Plenary meeting	TBD	F2F
January 2025	Plenary meeting	TBD	Virtual
June 2025	Plenary meeting	TBD	F2F
January 2026	Plenary meeting	TBD	Virtual
September 2026	Plenary meeting	TBD	F2F

3.3 Project events

MYRTUS committed to the project events:

- **MYRTUS intermediate event** - it will include an exhibition to present the intermediate results and a technical session showing MYRTUS technology.
 - *Held at the CPS Summer School, around M20*
- **TWO MYRTUS final Events** to present final results to both the scientific and industrial communities.
 - Scientific event - held at HiPEAC
 - Industrial event – held at Embedded World

Consortium partners committed to attend the project events.

3.4 Project reviews

By Grant Agreement, three Project Review are currently planned.

Refer to MYRTUS **Grant Agreement**, Section PROJECT REVIEWS.

3.5 Deliverables

The deliverables are the tool to reports the project results. Here we describe the process to follow for the preparation, approval and submission of deliverables.

The complete list of deliverables is reported in the **Grant Agreement** (Table **LIST OF DELIVERABLES**).

3.5.1 Preparation process and timeline

Work preparation includes preparing the Table of Content and has no major constraints (meant that can be prepared with large advance, if the WP leader and the Deliverable Leader need to do so for organisations purposes). The following two are HARD deadlines:

- **2 months before submission:** the ToC MUST be final and the request for contributions is sent to consortium partners.
- **3 weeks before submission:** the deliverable MUST be ready for internal review.

3.5.2 Internal review: approval process and timeline

For each deliverable, two reviewers are appointed (one from research one from industry). The approval process is subjected to the following HARD deadlines:

- **3 weeks before submission:** the reviewers receive the deliverable directly from the deliverable leader.
- **2 weeks before submission:** The reviewers complete their work, providing constructive comments and proposal for improvement.
- The deliverable leader has **two weeks to apply the review feedback** and upload the final PDF in the shared folder naming convection.

The location where to update the final deliverable is placed in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Official Documents -> Final deliverables*.

The reviewers' names are reported in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Official Documents -> Final deliverables -> Deliverable Leaders and Reviewers.xlsx*.

For an overview on how to navigate the Shared Drive Folder, consult *Section 4.2 – Project repository of this document*.

3.5.3 Deliverable in a critical path

In case of potential delay that could have a negative impact on the deliverable and in general on the achievements of the project, it is **declared a critical path**. The critical path can be declared:

- By the **WP leader**, when the delay is due to a delay in WP activities and result achievements. The WP leader declare the delay as soon as possible, in any case coordinators are expected to receive the information before the ToC definition.
- When the **reviewers** value a deliverable as 'Rejected deliverable'.

Deliverable/WP in critical paths trigger a direct intervention of coordinators that will support the WP leader or deliverable leader on the solution funding and, if necessary, communicate the issue to the PO.

3.6 Project reporting

Continuous reporting: beneficiaries have to continuously report on the progress actions, in accordance with *Grant Agreement, Article 21.1*.

Periodic reporting: beneficiaries must provide reports to request payments, in accordance with *Grant Agreement, Article 21.2*.

MYRTUS has two official reporting periods, as follows:

RP1 from month 1 to month M18 (1/01/2024 – 30/06/2024)

RP1 from month M19 to month 36 (1/07/2024 - 31/12/2026)

The Project Coordinator must submit a periodic report within 60 days following the end of each reporting period, and a final report within 60 days following the end of the action. Each report must be prepared by the Project Coordinator and the beneficiaries of the Consortium together, accordingly with the following process.

3.6.1 Preparation process and timeline

The preparation timeline is aligned with the one defined for Project Deliverables (see Section 3.5.1)

3.6.2 Internal review and final editing

3 weeks before submission, the document will be ready for the internal review and final editing that will be carried out by the coordination team.

3.7 Risk Management

Potential risks have been identified in the MYRTUS *Grant Agreement, Table LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS*.

The Project Coordinator, supported by the Scientific Coordinator and in collaboration with the WP leaders, shall be responsible for ensuring that risks are routinely monitored and maintained updated throughout the project lifecycle.

WP Leaders shall be responsible for the risk assessment within their work packages. When a new risk is identified by a partner, it should be reported to the WP Leader, Project Coordinator and Scientific Coordinator, who will then start the above-mentioned procedure.

The updated list of risks will always be available in the *SyGMA Portal*.

4 Documentation Management

The infrastructure chosen to hold the documentation produced by the project has been set up in google drive, through the Abinsula tools.

4.1 Document Templates, Naming convention and Versioning

4.1.1 Templates

- The following **templates** have been prepared, together with instructions to import and use them:
 - Document [Word]
 - Presentations [PowerPoint]
 - Posters [PowerPoint]
- Official **Project and Partners LOGOs** have been made available. Regarding partners logos, each partner is responsible of update their logos, in case any changes is necessary.
- MYRTUS reference colors are provided.
- The statement and disclaimer for external communication is provided in the file *MYRTUS acks*. Project communication, dissemination and visibility is **ruled by the Grant Agreement, article 17**.

These documents are available in the **Shared Drive Folder**, at the following path: *Management-> Organization->Templates*.

4.1.2 Document naming and versioning

The **project documents** shall follow the naming convention:

MYRTUS – YYYY.MM.DD – Short Title_Vx.y

Where YYYY is the year, MM is the month, DD is the Day.

In case of **deliverables**, this convention is simplified as follows:

MYRTUS - DX.Y - Short Title_Vx.y

where X and Y are the numbers related to each deliverable.

Document versioning is regulated by the **Vx.y** convention, where **x** is the version major number and **y** is the version minor number.

4.2 Project Repository

The shared project repository is structured as follows:

- **Management**
 - ■ **Official Documents**
 - ■ **Agreements**
 - 📄 Grant agreement
 - 📄 Consortium agreement
 - ■ **Amendments**
 - ■ **Periodic Reporting**
 - ■ **Final deliverables**
 - 📄 Deliverable Leaders and Reviewers
 - 📄 MYRTUS Dx.y
 - 📄 MYRTUS Gantt
 - 📄 MYRTUS D13.1 - Handbook
 - ■ **Organization**
 - ■ **Consortium**
 - 📄 MYRTUS mailing lists
 - 📄 Reference contacts
 - ■ **Templates**
 - ■ **logos**
 - ■ **partners logos**
 - ■ **Abinsula**
 - ■ **UNICA**
 - ■ ...
 - ■ **project logos**
 - ■ **template documents**
 - 📄 MYRTUS - deliverable_template.dotx
 - 📄 MYRTUS - presentation_template.potx
 - 📄 README - How to import and use the templates
 - 📄 MYRTUS acks
 - 📄 MYRTUS reference colours
 - ■ **Meetings**
 - ■ **F2F meetings**
 - ■ **YYYY.MM.DD - <PLACE OF THE MEETING>**
 - ■ **Organization**
 - 📄 participants
 - 📄 logistic information
 - ■ **presentations**
 - ■ **posters**
 - 📄 Agenda
 - 📄 Meeting minutes
 - ■ **Monthly meeting (video calls)**
 - 📄 MYRTUS - YYYY.MM.DD - Monthly meeting minutes
 - ■ **Review meetings**
 - ■ **YYYY.MM.DD**

WPX

- **Deliverables**
 - MYRTUS - DX.Y
- **Technical documents**
- **Meetings**
 - MYRTUS - YYYY.MM.DD - Presentation
 - MYRTUS - YYYY.MM.DD - WPX minutes

WP11-12 - Communication-Dissemination-Exploitation

- **Data Management**
 - Data Management Plan
 - Monitoring of Data release
- **and Communication material**
 - **Presentations**
 - **Press**
 - **Printed Material**
 - **Published Papers**
 - **Videos**
- **Open Access Management**
- **Synergies**
- MYRTUS-Dissemination&Exploitation_MonitoringTool

4.3 Zenodo

A MYRTUS Community has been created in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/myrtus/>